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FINAL DISSERTATION

MODELLING OF GENE EXPRESSION DATA USING EVOLVING SPIKING NEURAL NETWORK-A CASE STUDY ON NUTRIGENOMICS PROBLEM

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Gautam Kishore Shahi, declare that this thesis titled, ‘Modelling of Gene Expression Data Using Evolving Spiking Neural Network- A case study on Nutrigenomics Problem’ and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- This work was done wholly or mainly while in candidature for a master degree at this University.
- Where any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. With the exception of such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.
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Date:

“If you can think you can do it, you can.”

John Burroughs

Abstract

The work presents a methodology to assess the problems behind static gene expression data modelling and analysis with machine learning techniques. As a case study, transcriptomic data collected during a longitudinal study on the effects of diet on the expression of oxidative phosphorylation genes was used. Data were collected from 60 abdominally overweight men and women after an observation period of eight weeks, whilst they were following three different diets. Real-valued static gene expression data were encoded into spike trains using Gaussian receptive fields for multinomial classification using an evolving spiking neural network (eSNN) model. Results demonstrated that the proposed methodology can be used for predictive modelling of static gene expression data and future works are proposed regarding the application of eSNNs for personalised modelling.

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Abbreviations

SNN	Spiking Neural Networks
eSNN	Evolving Spiking Neural Networks
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
STDP	Spike Timing Dependent Plasticity
SVM	Support Vector Machines
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
deSNN	Dynamic Evolving Spiking Neural Network
STBD	Spatio-and spectro-temporal brain data
LTP	Long-Term Potentiation
LTD	Long-Term Depression
PSP	Post-Synaptic Potential
LIF	Leaky Integrate and Fire
ECoS	Evolving Connectionist Systems
EA	Evolutionary Algorithms
STBD	Spatio and Spectro Temporal Brain Data
PSNM	Probabilistic Spiking Neural Model
LIF	Leaky Integrate and Fire Model
LTP	Long Term Potentiation
LTD	Long Term Depression
BMI	Body Mass Index
MUFAs	Monounsaturated Fatty Acids
SFA	Saturated fatty Acid
MED	Mediterranean Diet
PBMC	Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cell

OXPHOS Oxidative Phosphorylation

mRMR Minimum Redundancy Maximum Relevance

Chapter 1

Introduction

The architecture of the evolving spiking neural network (eSNN) was proposed by Kasabov [11]. The eSNN is a kind of Evolving Connectionist Systems (ECoS) [12]. EcoS based procedure describes a class of constructive ANN algorithm that changes the structure and connection weights of the neural network in the training phase to adapt to the input information encoded. This behaviour is based on biological neurons, which can evolve and adapt according to their input [13]. The EcoS network is evolving in nature and uses one pass learning algorithm.

Biomedical research is one of the most significant areas of investigation in data science. This area produces a tremendous amount of data and provides an opportunity for extensive exploration and application in several domains, such as personalised medicine. Personalised modelling is now a trend and is considered beneficial for diagnosis, treatments, and advance in medical science [14, 15]. The current size of bioinformatics data collected for analysis and personalised medicine was estimated at around 75 petabytes in 2015, and is expected to grow tremendously [16]. Data scientists are continuously proposing novel methods for the analysis of such data. In this respect, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) have demonstrated their potential for the analysis of biological data and their application in personalised medicine in a cost-effective way [17].

There are different sources of bioinformatics data; one of them is gene expression data. Modelling of gene expression data is challenging in terms of time-costs and reliable results [18]. Several researchers have tried to tackle these problems by developing new methodologies for gene data modelling and analysis, [19] using Evolving Spiking Neural Networks (eSNN) [6, 20–23].

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The eSNN demonstrate their potential to handle different types of data ([6, 22, 24]), yet they have never been applied for static gene expression data modelling and classification. This research work proposes a computational model for static gene expression data analysis and predictive modelling using eSNN techniques. A case study on nutrigenomics problem has been done. The proposed computational model is able to reduce the curse of dimensionality. As such, the research problem can be stated as *"Given a static gene expression dataset, can evolving Spiking Neural Networks be used efficiently to analyse and classify it?"*

1.2 Objective of the Study

The objective of the study is to build a computational model for the analysis and classification of static gene expression data which can replace the current statistical modelling for analysis of biomedical data. In later stages, we have implemented our model as a case study on nutrigenomics problem. A set of signature genes has been obtained to reduce the features dimensionality. The wrapper approach combines a classification method with a generic optimisation algorithm, for which Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) are commonly used. The optimisation task for the EA consists of the identification of an optimal feature subset, which maximises the classification accuracy determined by the classifier

1.3 Significance of the study

In the study, we demonstrate how we can analyse static gene expression data using spiking neural networks for the study of gene expression data. The proposed methodology can speed up the computation time and results for the analysis of the static gene expression data. The methodology used in this work reduces computation costs as well as computation time.

1.4 Research Questions

The first step towards doing the research was building a set of research questions. Finding the answers to these questions helped to either progress in the right direction or got a correct set of results. The research questions that have been covered in this research work are:

- Can we replace traditional ANN techniques with a promising computational model based on eSNN for gene expression data analysis?

-
- What are the benefits of using eSNN versus traditional ANN?
 - Can we discriminate different types of diets by using the proposed computational model and a set of signature genes selected from the multitude of features available?
 - Can the computational model proposed to be applied to nutrigenomics data to build a predictive model for the identification of weight-related genetic issues?
 - Using the above-proposed model, can weight-related issues be detected at an early stage?

1.5 Methodology

We have applied the evolving spiking neural network for the building of the computational model, we have also applied preliminary techniques for data cleaning and formalisation of the static gene expression data.

1.6 Thesis Structure

The thesis documentation is organised in five chapters as follows :

Chapter 1 is the introduction which includes the motivation, the problem statement and the contributions of the research,

Chapter 2 is an elaborate description of what are Spiking Neural Networks, how do they work, their learning methods and models,

Chapter 3 is the methodology for data preprocessing, oversampling and feature selection,

Chapter 4 shows the application of Spiking Neural Networks, the classification results obtained and the gene interaction network,

Chapter 5 closes with the conclusions derived from the thesis work, applications of the work done, and the potential future works for this research project.

1.7 Summary

This introductory chapter gives a background to the problems, and the motivations that lead to the research presented in this thesis, the aims of the study are presented, the research questions are identified, and the contribution that this thesis brought about to research is outlined here.

Chapter 2

Spiking Neural Networks

The human brain is a highly complex and dense network. It contains approximately 100 billion (10^{11}) interconnected basic processing units called neurons. The neurons can interact with each other through the interchange of electrical pulses, called spikes. Inspired by the belief to understand better the truly excellent information processing abilities of the brain, numerous biologically feasible mathematical models have been invented in recent decades. Conventionally the Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) presume that the neural code transforms information between neurons based on an average rate of spike emission. Increasing proof from recent neurobiological investigation suggests that the accurate timing of spikes play a significant role in neural information processing [25–27].

The major contribution to the overall brain study and particularly to brain data analysis is the creation of a common coordinate system that can be used for a standardised study of brain data from different subjects and collected by different methods. Spatio-temporal activity in the brain is dependent on the internal brain structure, on the external stimuli and on the dynamics at gene/protein level. These methods have been tested using a variety of existing machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machines(SVM), Multilayer Perceptron(MLP), Bayesian Methods and many more. The most interesting point is that none of the algorithms works efficiently in case of static gene expression data to capture spatio-temporal relationships from spectro-temporal brain data (STBD) nor have they been able to accommodate prior knowledge about the brain in the models.

2.1 Spiking Neurons

Biological Neurons

A neuron is basically composed of three parts: axon, synapse, and dendrites. A synapse makes contact with a dendrite at the end of an axon. The contact results in an inter-neuronal signal, which can be either a chemical diffusion or an electrical impulse. The impulses can be measured using values. If the level of impulse value meets a certain threshold, firing of neuron takes place which is referred to as a spike. The incoming impulse signal from each neuron can be either excitatory or inhibitory, where excitatory means a help in the firing process and inhibitory means a hinder in the firing process. The condition of causing firing is that the excitatory signal should exceed the inhibitory signal by a certain amount in a short period of time, called the period of latent summation. The excitatory and inhibitory signals carry weights with them. An excitatory signal carries positive weights while inhibitory signals carry negative weights with them. A neuron is shown in Fig. 2.1

FIGURE 2.1: A Biological Neuron [1].

FIGURE 2.2: Stages of Neuron [2].

The neural system of the consists of three stages: receptors, a neural network, and effectors. Stimuli is received externally from an outer world or internally via the receptors. The information contained in the stimuli is then passed in the form of electrical impulses into the neurons. The neural network then processes the inputs and makes a proper decision for the outputs. Finally, the effectors translate electrical impulses from the neural network into responses to the outside environment, the Fig. 2.2 shows the three stages.

2.2 Neural Models

Hodgkin Huxley Model

In 1952, the English scientists Alan L. Hodgkin and Andrew Huxley [28] studied the electrochemical forces that mediated neural signalling in axons of a squid as shown in Fig. 2.3. Their study described the initialization and propagation of the action potential through the cell membrane through the ionic current created by sodium cations and potassium cations and a small leakage current created by Chlorine anions and/or other ions control. This mechanism is described as an electrical circuit, which consists of a capacitor C , input sources I , resistors R and batteries E .

FIGURE 2.3: Hodgkin Huxley Model[3].

Izhikevich Spiking Model

The transmitter-activated ion channel synapses are an evolution of the Hodgkin-Huxley model [29]. This model proposes synaptic modifications based on neurotransmitter release and on the consequent activation of their neuroreceptors. These are responsible for the onset of either excitatory or inhibitory postsynaptic currents, named EPSC and IPSC respectively. Transmitters-activated ion channels synapses are described as time dependent, as the channels conductivity depends on the arrival of a presynaptic action potential.

Leaky Integrate and Fire Model (LIF)

The Integrate-and-Fire model [30] shown in Fig. 2.4, adds to the constant potential above a decaying period term. When no incoming spike is received by the neuron, then this potential is subtracted from the membrane potential over time. A leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) spike is emitted at time when its potential reaches a threshold.

After a spike is emitted, and the membrane potential is reset to an initial state. The membrane potential can have a certain leakage between spikes, which is defined by a temporal parameter. In this period, no new spike can be emitted as the current is hyperpolarised.

FIGURE 2.4: Leaky Integrate and Fire Model [4].

Probabilistic Spiking Neural Model (PSNM)

In 2010, N. Kasabov [31] proposed the probabilistic spiking neural model (pSNM). This model adds three probabilistic constraints to the synaptic connection weight $w_{i,j}(t)$. The addition is explained in Fig.2.5 and calculated as:

- a probability $P_{ci,j}(t)$ that a spike emitted from the presynaptic neuron i will reach the postsynaptic neuron j .
- a probability $P_{si,j}(t)$ that a synapse $s_{i,j}$ contributes to the $PSP_j(t)$ after a spike is received, due to biochemical processes involved in the synaptic mechanism.
- a probability $P_j(t)$ that j will emit a spike after the threshold of the total $PSP_j(t)$ has been reached, which is known as the probability density for firing in a neural cell.

FIGURE 2.5: Probabilistic Spiking Neural Model (PSNM)[5].

2.3 Neural Encoding

This section addresses the possibility of an observer to understand neural activities and information transformation. Pulse codes and rate codes are the two existing theories in regard to understanding neural encoding. Both of the theories are explained below:

Pulse Codes

The first type of neural encoding is referred to as a spike or pulse code. It is assumed that the information carrier in this case is the precise spike times [32]. Computer simulations provide the evidence for temporal correlations between spikes.

The timing of the first spike after a reference signal is called time-to-first-spike. The most information about a stimulus is carried by the early spikes.

Rate Codes

The Rate Code theory assumes that the mean firing rate of a neuron carries the most, maybe even all the information of a transmission and are referred to as the 'rate codes' [33]. This theory has inspired the classical perceptron approaches. here, the mean firing rate is calculated as the ratio of the average number of spikes observed over a specific time interval. Sensory neural systems have exploited this concept extensively, yet the idea of mean firing rate has been constantly criticised, because temporal averaging of spikes cannot be used to explain the extremely short response times of the brain for certain stimuli. Also, it is well known that a visual stimuli require a moderate number of neural layers.

2.4 Learning Rules

Three learning paradigms can be distinguished in Spiking Neural Networks. These are supervised, unsupervised and reinforced. Hebbian learning is the most commonly used unsupervised learning algorithm. The spike-timing dependent plasticity (STDP) also belongs to the unsupervised category. An input-output mapping is required by supervised learning techniques. Two learning methods have been explained below.

Spike-Timing Dependent Plasticity (STDP)

The Hebb's law [34] states that "When an axon of cell A is near enough to excite cell B and repeatedly or persistently takes part in firing it, some growth process or metabolic change takes place in one or both cells such that A's efficiency, as one of the cells firing B, is increased."

The timing of pre-synaptic and post-synaptic activity [35–37] of a neuron affects the synaptic efficacy of brain. The strengthening of efficacy is called long-term potentiation(LTP) whereas the weakening of efficacy is referred to as long term depression(LDP). STDP is a function that recognises a fractional change of synaptic weights and is dependent on the difference between the arrival time of a presynaptic spike and the time post of an action potential emitted. This function is also known as the STDP window.

Spike Back Propagation (Spike-Prop)

Multilayer perceptron employ gradient based descent to modify synaptic weights in order to impose a certain input-output mapping on the network. But special assumptions are required to develop a back-propagation version for spiking neurons due to the fact that the topological recurrence of SNN and their explicit time dependence do not allow a straightforward evaluation of the gradient in the network.

Spike-Prop [38, 39] is a back-propagation algorithm proposed for SNN training. The aim of the method is to learn a set of desired firing times t_j^d of all output neurons j for a given input pattern presented to the network.

2.5 Application of Spiking Neural Networks

Application of SNN has traditionally been in the areas of neuroscience. The first of the studies and experimentation was done by Hodgkin and Huxley. Their study demonstrated that the anatomy of human brain plays a major role to implement neural networks. Thus, a comprehensive knowledge of organisation of individual neurons and classes of cells, alongwith the biochemical and molecular biology of enzymes, and genes that participate in brain development and maintenance, and growth

factor is crucial. There are numerous models for analysing the anatomical structure of brain for this purpose. NEURON3¹ and GENESIS4² being the most prominent ones. Modelling and simulation are fundamental for the understanding of neural processes.

2.6 Evolving Spiking Neural Networks

ECoS procedure has a long history, numerous modifications have been done, and some of the applications include fuzzy neural networks [40], dynamically evolving fuzzy systems [41] and self-organising maps [42]. ECoS is discussed in detail in the textbook by Kasabov.

The initial version of eSNN [43] was designed for visual pattern recognition. The procedure of classification is built on a simplified form of the integrate-and-fire neural model first presented in [44]. The model was invented to emulate the information processing of the human eye and was applied to a face recognition task. The results show a competitive performance in comparison to several other pattern recognition methods in the area [11].

The eSNN can be applied to a variety of classification problems due to its generic nature, some of the examples are text-independent speaker authentication [45] and experiment on the speech data of VidTIMIT audio-visual database [46], and visual data was later implemented to analyse the character of another version of the eSNN. The visual part of the same database was then used to study the characteristics of another extension of eSNN. After that, several other extensions and applications of eSNN have been proposed.

For the classification of real valued datasets, they need to be converted into a vector representation. An encoding technique is then applied on the vector of real valued elements to map them into a sequence of spikes. An encoding algorithm according to one's choice can be used or the choice of encoding algorithm can be optimised according to model's performance. Most commonly, when using eSNN, a rank order population encoding is employed. An eSNN is organised in several layers and is a feed-forward network. Weights between the neurons of the output layer and the neurons of either hidden layer or the input layer can be modified according to model's requirement and performance.

The following sections explain an encoding principle used in eSNN and is followed by the description of the one-pass learning method and the overall functioning of the eSNN method.

Rank order population encoding

Rank order population encoding is an extension of the rank order encoding introduced by Thorpe [47]. Real valued elements are mapped into a sequence of spikes. An implementation based on arrays of

¹<https://neuron.yale.edu/neuron/>

²<http://genesis-sim.org/>

receptive fields is firstly described by Bohte [48]. Receptive fields are used to encode each continuous input variable independently by a group of M-dimensional receptive fields. This is done by using a collection of neurons with overlapping sensitivity profiles. For a variable n an interval $[I_{max}^n - I_{min}^n]$ is defined. The Gaussian receptive field of neuron i is given by its centre C_j [49], calculated as:

$$C_j = I_{min}^n + \frac{(2j - 3)}{2} * \frac{(I_{max}^n - I_{min}^n)}{(N - 2)} \quad (2.1)$$

and its width W_j [49], calculated as:

$$W_j = \frac{1}{\beta} * \frac{(I_{max}^n - I_{min}^n)}{(N - 2)} \quad (2.2)$$

with $1 \leq \beta \leq 2$. The width of each Gaussian receptive field parameter .

One-Pass Learning

One-pass learning outputs neurons with class label $l \in L$, where L is the set of class labels of the given dataset. The number and value of class labels depends on the classification problem to solve. When a certain input sample is presented to the network, propagation of spike train takes place through the SNN, resulting in firing of neurons.

2.7 Summary

In this chapter we did a literature review of the Spiking Neural Network, evolving Spiking Neural Network, encoding schemes, and learning models of the Spiking Neural Network.

Chapter 3

Implementation using Evolving Spiking Neural Network

Our primary goal is to build a computational model for gene expression data to reduce the time for analysis of static gene expression data.

Experimentation was done on gene expression data to assess the performance of the algorithm. Python implementation of the algorithms was used for all eSNN experiments on dataset while NeuCom[50] was used for testing using traditional machine learning algorithms.

3.1 Architecture of Evolving Spiking Neural Network

Gaussian Receptive Fields

Population encoding combined with arrays of receptive fields make it possible to represent continuous input value with graded and overlapping Gaussian activation functions [39] mimicking the behaviour of biological sensory neurons [6, 13, 39]. To encode static values into temporal patterns, it is sufficient to divide the range of possible values into several overlapping Gaussian segments, relating one neuron to each segment. Stimulation of a neuron will be greater when the static value belongs to its segment or nearby segments. Then, early spikes are assigned to those neurons that are highly stimulated, and later to those neurons that are less stimulated. Temporal encoding of static values achieves both sparse codings, by assigning firing times to significantly activated neurons only, and effective event-based network simulation [51]. Additionally, it achieves a coarse coding by encoding each variable independently, as every input is encoded by an optimal number of neurons [39]. Gaussian receptive fields permit encoding of static inputs by applying a number of neurons with overlapping sensitivity functions, where each input data is binarized by N dimensional receptive fields.

For an input variable a range of minimum and maximum value is defined as I_{min}^n and I_{max}^n respectively. For neuron j , the Gaussian receptive field can be defined by its centre C_j , calculated as:

$$C_j = I_{min}^n + \frac{(2j - 3)}{2} * \frac{(I_{max}^n - I_{min}^n)}{(N - 2)} \quad (3.1)$$

and its width W_j , calculated as:

$$W_j = \frac{1}{\beta} * \frac{(I_{max}^n - I_{min}^n)}{(N - 2)} \quad (3.2)$$

with $1 \leq \beta \leq 2$. The parameter β directly regulates the width of every Gaussian field. Classification accuracy of the model can be improved by adjusting the centre, the width and the number of receptive fields.

FIGURE 3.1: Overall of architecture of eSNN [6].

3.1.1 Evolving Spiking Neural Networks

As shown in Fig. 3.1, the architecture of an eSNN model can be divided into three layers: an encoding layer; a hidden layer for supervised learning; and an evolving output neural model for data classification. In the input layer, the input static gene data is fed to the network, where it is encoded into spike events. Here, a number of overlapping Gaussian receptive functions is implemented to

transform the input into spike sequences to represent the first layer of neurons. Equations 3.1 and 3.2 are used to compute the centre and width of the Gaussian, which influence the firing intensity of the receptive function. In the hidden layer, the encoded value is presented to a pre-synaptic neuron and the receptive field with the highest related value generates the first spike.

$$\tau_i = [T(1 - Output_j)] \quad (3.3)$$

where T is the simulation or spike time interval. The neurons of the hidden and output layer are completely connected. In the evolving output neural model, spiking neurons evolve during training to represent input spike trains that correspond to the same class. Connection weights change during learning. The eSNN architecture is based on Thorpe’s model [52], as this uses the timing of the incoming spike to adjust neural connection weights. More specifically, earlier spikes denote stronger connection weights as opposed to later spikes. A neuron spikes if its post-synaptic potential (PSP) reaches a threshold as per Equation 3.4.

$$PSP_i = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if fired} \\ \sum w_{ji} * mod^{order(j)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.4)$$

where w_{ji} represents the weight of a synaptic connection between pre-synaptic neuron j to the output neuron i , mod is the modulation factor ($0 \leq mod \leq 1$) and function $order(j)$ is the rank of the spike emitted by neuron j . Single pass feedforward learning is applied to the output neurons. Each input data point is assigned to an output neuron, which has a weight and threshold value associated and stored in the neuron repository. This weight is compared to the weight of other neurons in the network to check for similarity. If the similarity is greater than a defined threshold, then this weight will be updated with the weight and threshold of the most similar neuron, otherwise, it evolves a new one. This is computed by calculating the average between the new output neuron weight vector and the merged neuron weight vector, and the average between the new output neuron threshold and the merged neuron threshold respectively. After merging, the trained vector is discarded and not stored in the repository. After learning, testing is performed by passing the test sample spikes to all the trained output neurons. The output neuron that fires first is associated to a class label defined by the test sample.

As with any learning algorithm, the configuration of parameters has a profound effect on the performance of evolving spiking neural network [53]. Some of the main parameters of the eSNN model are

- **Receptive Fields** The receptive field does a significant portion of data processing at the input layer. The collection of neurons in an array of the receptive field have overlapping sensitivity

profiles. In a population-based encoding scheme, it is responsible for encoding real-valued input data into spike trains that are then fed to the network. Increasing the number of receptive fields enables to better distinguish between data samples, but this leads to increased computation cost. On the other hand, a lower value for this parameter would result in faster processing but at the cost of reduced accuracy. It also decreases the width of the fields, making the response more localised. This, in turn, might lead to the addition of more neurons to the network.

- **Modulation factor** This parameter controls the initial weights which in turn affects the contribution of each spike to the postsynaptic potential. The modulation factor is given a value between 0 and 1. If the value is closer to 1, the contribution of the spike to the postsynaptic potential would be a continuous exponential function, whereas lesser values would lead to the contribution of decaying exponentially. Consequently, a value of 0 for this parameter would mean that the postsynaptic potential is not affected by the presynaptic spikes. On the other hand, if the modulation factor is 1, then all spikes would equally contribute to the postsynaptic potential. The modulation factor determines how intensely the order of spike timing affects a neuron.
- **Similarity** This parameter defines a threshold value based on which the output layer neurons are created or updated. If the weight of a new output neurons is similar to the defined threshold, then the new neuron is merged with the most similar neuron in the repository. In this study, the similarity between neuronal weights is measured using Euclidean distance. The values for similarity are specified between 0 and 1. Lower values for this parameter results in fewer neurons being created and higher values would generate an output neuron for each input sample leading to overfitting.
- **Threshold** The firing threshold is calculated as a fraction of the maximum PSP. This is derived using a parameter c with a value between 0 and 1. Lower values of the fraction c would result in reducing the firing threshold which in turn advances the response of a neuron. The firing threshold γ_i could be defined as $\text{PSP}_{\max(i)} * C$

3.2 Nutrigenomics

Nutrigenomics is an emerging field that unfolds relationships between the role of nutrition and their effects on human health and their response to diseases. It integrates the science of bioinformatics and nutrition to study changes at gene and molecular level [54].

With the advent of the increased poor lifestyle and negligence towards one's health, nutrigenomics became a hot topic of research. Nowadays due to the advancement of the technology, people have

access to more knowledge about different types of food and their effect on human health. The awareness has caused people all over the world to become conscious of what they are consuming, yet due to an imbalanced food habit, are suffering from health related issues, such as obesity, overweight, cardiovascular diseases, etc. Some of the facts about the nutrigenomics problem¹ are-

- Nutrigenomics is an entire system approach, it examines the relationship between diets and their associated risks and reaction to diseases, and effect on molecular mediators of the human body.
- Many types of tool can be used to identify disease risk and advancement to record nutrient input. We can maintain food diaries, to understand the body's reaction to point the possible gene variants. Gene assay can be used for monitoring the impact of food by analysing clinical data like weight, sex, age and BMI.
- Nutrigenomics approach can be applied to a wide range of situations like links between obesity and mental health of the body, trying to find a correlation between consuming diet (nutrient) and diseases, such as alcohol and its effect on the Kidney. Moreover, it can be used to make a better diet plan according to the human body condition.
- Nutrigenomics can be used to provide personalised interventions to advise consuming the food type according to a person's body, to advise proper diet consumption during a particular body condition, for e.g. a particular diet for pregnancy.
- Nutrigenomics is complicated. We do not have a concrete model to analyse nutrigenomic biomarkers. In case of genomic assays, it is difficult to state which tissue should be analysed, and how are nutrient and gene expression data correlated. Food diaries are not reliable for nutrigenomic problems.

To deal with the nutrigenomics problem like obesity, overweight, we are lagging in terms of technology, and it is a common problem throughout the world. Carelessness of food habits and poor lifestyle choices lead to eating unhealthy foods which in turn leads to overweight, obesity and weight related problems.

Weight health is calculated by one's Body Mass Index (BMI). BMI is directly dependent on the weight of the body and height. BMI is measured by dividing an individual's weight by the square of the individual's height. The formula to calculate BMI is:

$$BMI = \frac{m}{h^2} \quad (3.5)$$

where m is weight of the human body in kg and h is the height of the body in cm.

¹<https://www.genomicseducation.hee.nhs.uk/news/item/290-nutrigenomics-your-genes-diet-health-what-you-need-to-know/>

FIGURE 3.2: BMI Chart[7]

When the calculated BMI for an individual is in the range $[25 - 30]$ kg/m², he/she is considered overweight, while a BMI range over 30 kg per metre square is considered as obese. Obesity is a medical state in which the weight of the human body grows over a certain threshold. In obesity, fat accumulates to an extent where it negatively affects the body. Obesity increases the probability of various diseases and conditions, particularly cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, obstructive sleep apnea, certain types of cancer, osteoarthritis, and depression. Some of the Asian and middle countries have low obesity rate while the western countries have a high rate of obesity. If the BMI is less than 18.5 the person is considered as underweight, a range between 18.5 to 24.9 is considered healthy. The BMI categorization is shown in Fig. 3.2. Around 300 million people are obese in the world and 1 billion people are overweight. Some of the major causes of obesity are excessive food intake, lack of physical activity and genetic susceptibility.

In the current work, our main focus is on food type and generic information. The kind of food we consume affects our body. It is represented the obesity and overweight in 2005 across the country. Western countries are expected to become more obese compared to other countries. A major observation from the Fig. 3.3 is that people from the Western countries have a large number of overweight people. This difference is due to the fact that people in the Med region have good quality MUFA in their diet, whereas people from the Western countries lack these.

Similarly the Fig 3.4 shows how obesity is affecting people all over the world; if we see the graph of European countries in Fig. 3.5 then southern part of the Europe is less affected by obesity.

FIGURE 3.3: Worldwide age-standardized prevalence of overweight (upper) and obesity (lower) in adults 20 years and older by country in 2005 [8].

Obesity is normally caused by eating too much and moving too little in daily life. If a person consumes high amounts of energy, especially fats and sugars, but don't lose off the energy through exercise and physical activity, a considerable amount of the surplus energy will be stored as fat in the human body. The food we eat can be divided into three categories-

- Western Diet with Saturated Fatty Acid (SFA),
- Western Diet with monounsaturated fat (MUFA)
- Mediterranean Diet (MED)

The study shows that the Mediterranean Diet (MED) is good for health because it contains mainly plant-based food like fruits and vegetables, nuts, legumes etc., olive oil and canola oil (replacing butter), which is healthy for human body.

FIGURE 3.4: Data collected by the World Health Organisation shows that in 2014 there were high concentrations of obesity in every region of the world. [9]

3.3 Data Description

Gene expression data is collected using microarray techniques [55]. Microarray data represents matrices where the expression level of thousands of genes are measured simultaneously. For our case study, gene expression data was obtained from the publicly available Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) repository of functional genomics data (NCBI GEO [56] accession GSE30509; [57]). A Norwegian scientist published the data as an extension of his research demonstrating that saturated fatty acids contribute to obesity [58]. The data describes three types of diet: Western Diet with Saturated Fatty Acid (SFA), Western Diet with monounsaturated fat (MUFA) and Mediterranean Diet (MED). The Mediterranean (MED) diet is believed to be health-promoting due to its high content of MUFA and polyphenols [56]. Gene expression can be affected by these bioactive compounds, and therefore they can regulate pathways and protein related foods to cardiovascular disease interference. This research identified the effects of a MED-type diet, and the replacement of SFA with MUFA in a Western-type diet, on Peripheral Blood mononuclear Cell (PBMC) gene expression and plasma proteins. Overweight men and women with the abdominal distribution of fat were allocated to an eight-week, completely controlled SFA diet (19% daily energy as SFA), a MUFA diet (20% daily energy MUFA), or a MED diet (21% daily energy MUFA). Concentrations of 124 plasma proteins and PBMC whole-genome transcriptional profiles were assessed. Results demonstrated that consumption of MUFA and MED diets decreased the expression of oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) genes, plasma connective tissue growth factor, and apo-B concentrations when compared with the SFA diet. Moreover, the MUFA diet changed the expression of genes involved in B-cell receptor signaling and endocytosis signaling, when compared with the MED and SFA diets. Participants who consumed the MED diet had lower

Name	1007_s_at	1494_f_at	1552602_at	1558541_at	220102_at	220103_s_at	220107_s_at	220108_at	220112_at	220115_s_at	220116_at	220118_at	220119_at	220127_s_at	1558552_s_a	220129_at	220131_at	220134_at
Descrpt	DDRI	CYP2A6	CACNG5	CHU79_HUM	FOXJ2	CCDC98	C16orf140	GNAL4	ANKRD55	CDH10	KCNW2	ZBTB32	EPBA114A	FKRL12	SOHL2	FXYD1	QSOX4	
GSM7561	5.01555278	3.749011317	4.080043852	2.33399542	2.06310858	4.60572652	2.623168208	2.013818162	6.823616185	1.93425638	1.582208916	4.753972262	2.61138129	8.01350522	2.263417159	2.26110001	4.594542423	6.135
GSM7561	5.67522465	3.64361075	4.08309817	2.068369906	1.747177726	4.704313612	3.19659989	2.209934959	6.704252845	1.567836947	1.765111627	4.514741446	2.482750944	7.890469291	1.98895478	1.840231346	4.705269082	6.314
GSM7561	5.368051136	3.598564114	4.067367802	2.005914013	1.202474941	4.34619006	2.49769784	2.046605062	6.621322202	1.588893092	1.486156369	4.527922118	2.800805729	1.981708285	1.886537183	2.106486742	5.466923543	5.706
GSM7561	5.027376246	3.643988054	3.893253223	2.202293738	2.096608005	4.286694076	2.450387249	2.159817695	6.487686039	1.630812763	1.821400714	4.487110901	2.875869383	7.834611351	1.99241372	2.090164235	5.096146716	5.863
GSM7561	5.76745794	3.888312923	3.886867033	2.059542961	2.18878986	4.368002203	2.651094627	2.45663252	2.035903082	1.977021221	1.622683623	5.12209129	2.624830592	7.789841197	2.179307836	2.310921553	3.726703889	5.287
GSM7561	5.774979734	3.637795947	4.21011256	2.185329664	2.287855311	4.380394909	2.693653362	2.361734894	7.475615861	1.711222336	1.912580949	4.566098791	2.541422861	1.815544087	2.237981633	5.028910855	5.230	
GSM7561	5.995743603	3.560492556	3.860046384	2.09814226	2.075788336	4.319241525	2.428572024	2.247088318	5.401612185	1.776449943	1.583531297	4.330823402	2.714689992	7.824912766	2.026960743	1.994914164	4.989824839	5.408
GSM7561	5.639373791	3.621059277	3.659487746	2.023512056	1.958110695	4.561944777	2.483194751	1.918511351	5.964113215	1.651051762	1.716126849	4.549684232	4.459640435	7.902900081	2.065166444	1.940950151	4.942852271	5.919
GSM7561	5.95951066	3.816041722	4.026654674	2.72663039	2.303476348	4.361493817	3.000867081	2.265677393	8.053300819	1.785323594	1.734853374	4.870536106	5.91775405	7.727928524	2.350480177	2.293899653	5.124614689	5.762
GSM7561	5.90666725	3.798785625	4.107584895	2.39562287	1.99119684	4.311210045	2.664315308	2.380486602	5.737544604	1.703132565	1.708110352	4.38202636	4.241813243	7.807809543	1.984079497	2.174987282	4.982649571	5.559
GSM7561	5.673666099	3.778075956	3.928967707	2.176553732	2.104792939	3.357545673	2.704356093	2.116082175	7.171333594	1.581164045	1.625326372	4.320893636	2.251959257	8.080914655	2.714716471	1.957853634	5.6969828	6.073
GSM7561	5.671871993	3.696444169	4.274350535	2.671540625	2.021130743	4.69469082	2.569597918	2.400995217	7.569447971	1.80882851	1.704737894	4.467231025	4.489711116	7.995074006	2.37777265	2.067969633	5.070487628	6.299
GSM7561	5.87290766	3.735346157	3.792819454	2.181093187	2.075557729	4.284113112	2.474524299	2.031244236	7.194174319	1.482180021	1.727174695	4.400538106	2.65403271	7.740806602	2.020092005	1.904899999	4.774129348	5.786
GSM7561	5.620666488	3.636815185	4.055454285	2.07421795	1.955633895	4.530064581	2.561511434	2.102598542	7.423604946	1.47407415	1.613930464	4.270246062	2.36416911	7.950579492	1.957389451	2.047872737	5.127451598	5.913
GSM7561	5.883122352	3.552149888	4.651096662	1.940336937	2.269921519	4.417372083	2.251976215	2.500440879	4.876947433	1.829058995	1.754725579	4.078071891	3.226195036	6.008122927	2.21101121	2.357056377	5.241349728	4.82
GSM7561	5.498229335	3.88916033	3.958806894	2.307380971	2.296564825	4.50956263	2.472766378	2.430775531	5.492171459	1.896147686	1.957268589	4.539772905	3.119059249	7.48543227	1.8350692	2.05849202	5.415225271	6.155
GSM7561	5.907242735	3.701163012	3.734137076	2.29893119	2.29604574	4.123840278	2.74190175	2.425812885	6.638409449	1.818596099	1.762849006	4.651666542	2.425407896	7.860939458	2.470655239	2.14544791	5.369102979	5.488
GSM7561	5.967544821	3.811649361	4.154197879	2.041713632	2.109423336	4.567670414	2.453951876	2.465738013	6.691413547	2.148521942	1.93963759	4.370763365	2.807962059	8.054344667	2.308400178	2.350185931	4.765026854	5.377
GSM7561	5.791406553	3.748666838	4.181302642	2.267021844	2.004466195	4.404836757	2.581164654	2.206998069	6.147675953	1.540835781	1.600541471	4.560064438	2.385556229	7.182899016	2.206032428	2.11064767	4.978334255	5.66
GSM7561	5.543815057	3.421415498	4.188990158	2.444576183	2.317801092	4.347421208	2.635112257	2.143833348	6.107844285	1.862270286	1.885760736	4.636990681	2.594489319	7.950489924	2.183577954	2.214900156	4.878598105	5.726
GSM7561	5.769039095	3.528952264	4.282113794	2.437286462	2.204250422	4.48075128	2.48016116	2.339634072	7.380884061	1.595060623	1.845761056	4.539696467	2.575042374	7.850442985	2.613211466	2.035034059	4.641374073	6.384
GSM7561	5.788752882	3.729891558	4.181750677	2.641532483	2.055354953	4.252977451	2.832033896	2.208465473	6.194407848	1.705205229	2.102574074	4.16847685	2.986179356	7.966479282	1.66503089	2.29297812	4.665272527	5.881
GSM7561	5.954848236	3.901789974	4.058902317	1.985791526	1.883853362	4.122601572	2.462755056	2.234253635	6.394586362	1.654307406	1.5514841	4.501281078	6.63831278	7.692134529	2.106975642	2.263002879	4.60929186	5.85
GSM7561	5.757333797	3.836144399	4.061185401	2.411530083	1.936411336	4.124807959	2.480509375	2.960073475	5.890233774	1.719324393	1.993065953	4.458913051	2.737265246	7.865164373	2.056123042	2.333898905	4.575645231	5.7
GSM7561	5.581535045	3.410000335	3.895711292	2.22481055	1.882072664	4.79009807	2.560525265	2.096803835	9.44105311	1.752230377	1.491618577	4.515295433	2.455268007	7.62353848	1.875306099	2.204745276	4.195979006	6.722
GSM7561	5.514674265	3.284744878	3.82347135	2.143592893	1.991322868	4.539075437	2.609831073	2.053679159	5.909018678	1.500658238	1.703595613	4.540861558	2.663216164	7.905724816	2.146492106	2.085684155	4.510222587	6.467
GSM7561	5.002960202	3.92182645	4.360430136	2.349439161	2.462130236	4.00405295	2.882897202	2.709421467	4.54859662	2.008978014	1.731178693	4.777412448	2.758865793	7.818526664	2.37482693	2.228422909	5.211856233	4.872
GSM7561	6.043899487	3.977627772	4.129901411	2.243842156	1.902194901	4.024217262	2.354345033	2.623168208	5.494779276	1.73490095	1.790334876	4.314193711	7.744835305	7.69654146	2.258187475	2.289331073	4.345239594	5.364
GSM7561	5.031616018	3.91105734	4.020685775	2.28539115	2.64664532	3.95030852	2.637146708	2.89150626	7.02462237	1.762154789	1.790440139	4.39348337	2.89433588	8.067617396	2.04489325	2.1224705	4.556567732	5.339
GSM7561	6.032481176	3.281878244	3.885813514	2.53455774	2.206595983	4.345917946	2.937158285	2.189893151	7.139929203	1.92214949	1.712696651	4.504837546	2.805343458	7.89548801	2.557224112	2.370734943	4.64169309	6.321

FIGURE 3.6: Gene Expression Data.

to study and classify gene expression data, and the proposed computational model could be used as benchmark for gene expression data analysis for personalised modelling. Figure Shows a graphical representation of the experimental procedure designed for the eSNN system for static gene expression data analysis. Our proposed procedure is summarized in Fig. 3.7

FIGURE 3.7: Classification Model.

3.4.2 Dataset Selection

The proposed methodology is implemented on static gene expression data. Microarrays are one of the latest development in experimental molecular biology that can be used for monitoring of gene expression data for tens of thousands of genes in parallel and are already producing huge amounts of valuable data. We have collected our data for case study from Gene Expression Omnibus repository.

3.4.3 Data preprocessing

Preprocessing of data includes data cleaning, modification, and noise removal. In our experiments, the genePattern portal [59] provided by the Broad Institute is being used for analysis of the selected gene expression data.

-
- **Data Cleaning** The data which we have collected contains noise. Data cleaning involves processing of the initial data to convert it into a valid desired format to be fed into our computational model.
 - **Sampling** In the dataset we have only 60 series of data collected from 60 people, out of them 49 data are accurate as per the description given by the publisher of the data. We decided to oversample the available data due to very low number of accurate samples. Oversampling is the process of getting a similar dataset from the original data. We have extended our data to 98 data points. We have implemented our computational model on both the datasets and will observe the accuracy of the best one.

Feature selection

Feature selection plays a key role in machine learning, especially in cases of high-dimensional gene expression data, which consists of thousands of features with only a few numbers of samples. The primary goal of feature selection is to minimize the number of features without losing information. It deals with the issues of overfitting [60] and curse of dimensionality [55].

To get an unbiased classification result, it is necessary to minimize the curse of dimensionality. This process establishes which features are of high significance and which hold little to no importance. There are several feature selection algorithms across the domains, selecting a feature selection depends on several factors, the model we are using, data etc. Keeping in mind the available list of feature selection algorithm to deal with the large feature set, we have used both literature and algorithms to reduce the number of features.

The number of features can be selected by using one of the three procedure described below:

- The first, The most straightforward procedure is to select signatory features from literature by inspecting which features are the most valuable ones.
- The second method is to select features using the well-known features selection algorithm. Some of them are Maximum Relevance Minimum Redundancy (mRMR) [61], Multi-task Lasso (MT-LASSO) [62]. This algorithm ensures robustness and reliability.

To have an effective set of features, more than one algorithm is applied then. Then, either we can take a set union of all top-ranked features given by different algorithm and ultimately we get a reduced set of feature, or we can also take an intersection of selected features given by different algorithm, it can be a reliable set of features because it is driven from all features algorithm.

- Another approach could be the combination of above two methods, in which we first select the features from literature then we apply the feature selection as mentioned in the second approach, after that, a union or intersection of both can be taken as a list of features.

There is no fixed rule for these approaches, it depends on the classification model and the data, so the best way to minimise the feature is by experimenting with all possible approach and consider the feature which gives a good result.

In our case study, there were 23941 features and only 49 samples before preprocessing. The high number of features leads to the curse of dimensionality problem. For this work, we have applied the third approach to reducing the number of features, firstly, To solve the problem of high dimensionality, a set of 29 signature genes were selected, as indicated by the literature [57]. Then, a number of feature selection algorithms were applied to the original 23941 genes. For our work, we have used the Maximum Relevance Minimum Redundancy (mRMR) and Multi-task Lasso (MT-LASSO) algorithms. The top 50 features from both the algorithms were selected. Finally, the intersection of all three sets of genes was performed. This resulted in a final set of 26 genes.

The list of selected features and their description is obtained from GeneCards [63] is shown in Table 3.1.

TABLE 3.1: List of selected features.

Gene	Description
ATP5D	ATP Synthase F1 Subunit Delta
ATP5G3	ATP Synthase Membrane Subunit C Locus 3
ATP5L	ATP Synthase Membrane Subunit G
ATP6V1A	ATPase H+ Transporting V1 Subunit A
ATP6V1H	ATPase H+ Transporting V1 Subunit H
ATP6V1G1	ATPase H+ Transporting V1 Subunit G1
COX4I1	Cytochrome C Oxidase Subunit 4I1
COX7A2	Cytochrome C Oxidase Subunit 7A2
EDF1	Endothelial Differentiation Related Factor
COX8A	Cytochrome C Oxidase Subunit 8A
COX7C	Cytochrome C Oxidase Subunit 7C
NDUFA11	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit A11
NDUFA7	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit A7
NDUFA8	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit A8
NDUFAB1	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit AB1
NDUFB2	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit B2
NDUFB4	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit B4
NDUFB9	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit B9
NDUFS5	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit S5
NDUFS6	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit S6
TXN2	Thioredoxin 2
UQCRB	Ubiquinol-Cytochrome C Reductase Binding Protein
NDUFS7	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Core Subunit S7
TNNI2	Troponin I2, Fast Skeletal Type
NDUFS8	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Core Subunit S8
TCIRG1	T Cell Immune Regulator 1A

3.4.4 Applying eSNN model with Cross validation

The eSNN algorithm [64] creates a repository of output neurons for the training patterns. For each training pattern that belongs to the same class, a new output neuron is created and connected to all the presynaptic neurons in the previous layer. The weight for each of the connection from presynaptic neuron j to output neuron i is denoted as W_{ji} . The value of W_{ji} is calculated based on the spike order through a synapse j , $W_{ji} = \text{mod}^{\text{order}(j)}$, $\forall j$, where j is the presynaptic neuron of output neuron i . The threshold γ_i of newly created output neuron would be defined as the fraction $C \in \mathbb{R}$, $0 < C < 1$, of the Maximum postsynaptic potential is given by $PSP_{max(i)} : \gamma_i = PSP_{max(i)} * C$

The weight vector of newly created output neuron is then compared with the already trained output neurons in the repository. If the newly created output neuron weight vector is less than the sum of trained neuron weight vectors, then the threshold and weight vector of newly created output neuron is merged with the most similar neuron according to $w = \frac{w_{\text{new}} + w * N}{N+1}$

$$\text{and } \gamma = \frac{\gamma_{\text{new}} + \gamma * N}{N+1}$$

Here, N is the number of previous merges of the most similar neurons. After the merge operation, the newly created output neuron weight vector is discarded, and the new pattern is presented to model. If none of the trained neuron in the repository is similar, the new output neuron is added to the repository. The working model of this algorithm is implemented in Python and the code is given in Appendix.

3.4.5 Parameter optimization

The performance of the evolving spiking networks depends on the parameters of the learning model. Some of the main parameters of the eSNN are-

- Gaussian Receptive Fields, In the eSNN model, gaussian field is being used, significant part of data processing at the input layer is done by the respective field. The population based encoding being used converts real-valued input data into spike trains that are then fed to the network. Increasing the respective fields helps to distinguish between data samples, but it requires high computation cost. In another case, lowering the respective fields makes processing fast but decreases the accuracy of the model.
- Width, It also decreases the width of the fields making the response more localised. This in turn might lead to addition of more neurons to the network.
- The centre of the gaussian respective field also depends on the range of values, I_{\min}^n and I_{\max}^n with normalisation. It requires to assign the range of input values. For example, in this case, the range for I_{\min}^n and I_{\max}^n is [5,12].

3.4.6 Classification results evaluation

By using evolutionary computation algorithms, the highest classification accuracy is calculated with respect to the optimised combination of parameters.

To analyse the performance of our computational model, we have used a confusion matrix. The confusion matrix includes information about precision and recall and how many data supports the result.

3.5 Signatory Gene Selection

Then, we build a predictive model, by selecting a subset of genes from the already selected 26 features. This subset of features can in turn be used to construct a personalised model to detect weight related issues. This can be achieved by observing the least number of genes from Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells (PBMC) data.

FIGURE 3.8: An Algorithm for Signature Gene.

After evaluating the computational model, we created a Bin array containing combinations of (0,1) and then passed it to the selected features. The output was a list of features having minimum and maximum values. The minimum and maximum valued features obtained were passed to the best classification model. Optimisation of features was done using genetic algorithm. By selecting relevant genes, we will decrease the computational cost of the model and make it faster and more accurate. These genes could be used for decision support on diet-related issues. A diagram is used in Fig. 3.8 to summarise this procedure.

Algorithm for selecting all possible combination of features.

```
Set f= feature set
N=number of features
Create a BinaryArray(BinArray)
for i in range(1,N):
    shufflle the i with max value and 0 with min value of f
    do random shufflle for features
    return list
```

Example -

BinArray - [0,0,1]

Fmin-max - [1,2,89]

Output - [1,2,89]

After getting all possible combination of features. We have tested each set of the selected feature in our computational model using a genetic algorithm. Select the best combination of genes which are able to classify the data with high accuracy and prepare a list of Signatory gene.

3.6 Summary

In this chapter we have discussed about the architecture and working model of the evolving Spiking Neural Network, and the list of parameters governing it. We have also discussed about the data, source of dataset, steps involved in the cleaning and and sampling. This chapter discusses about the basic steps involved in the processing of the data before applying the machine learning algorithm on our computational model. We have discussed about the implementation of the proposed computational model. We have also discussed about the signature genes and the algorithms to generate it.

Chapter 4

Experimental Results

To evaluate our computational model, we have used F_1 score and accuracy. To compare the performance of our eSNN model, we have also applied other machine algorithms such as Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP).

Multilayer Perceptron

Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) is a network of interconnected neurons, a feedforward artificial neural network. A MLP has three layers, an input layer, a hidden layer and an output layer. The main principle of MLP is error back propagation. It works by adjusting the weights using error correction function in epochs until the expected result is achieved. The primary benefits of using MLP is that it does not take the probabilistic relationship of the features. There are some challenges while implementing MLP, like fixing the optimal value for learning rate and momentum to avoid convergence at local minima. The success of the model depends on parameter setting like the right number of hidden layers and the number of iterations. MLP works well on various kinds datasets, due to which it is considered as a universal approximator [65]. One of its disadvantages is the computational time increase on increasing the number of hidden layers.

With our dataset, the highest classification accuracy for MLP was obtained with 4 hidden layers and 12 neurons at each hidden layer.

Support Vector Machines (SVM)

SVM is a supervised machine learning algorithm. SVM can be used for classification and regression problems. The algorithm is suitable for a large number of features and a low number of data points. We plot the data point in an n -dimensional space, where n is the number of attributes in the dataset to find the hyperplane, and the hyperplane differentiates the data. For classification, we choose the best fitting hyperplane that separates the classes. We choose the hyperplane which maximises the margin between the two classes. One of the advantages of SVM is its efficient handling of high dimensional

features mainly if the number of features is greater than the number of data samples, but it needs high computational cost while dealing with a large number of features set.

4.1 Performance Measure

For performance evaluation, two measures are considered for all the experiments.

F1-Score is used to measure the test accuracy of a model; it considers both precision and recall. It is a combined metric derived from the values of precision and recall. Precision is the ratio of true positive and actual results (combination of true positive and false positive) and recall is defined as the ratio of true positive and predicted results (combination of true positive and false negative). Precision refers to a classifiers ability, and recall defines the classifiers potential to identify all the positive samples. The formula to calculate process, recall and F1 is given below.

$$Precision = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}} \quad (4.1)$$

$$Recall = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}} \quad (4.2)$$

$$F1 = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (4.3)$$

Accuracy is defined as the ratio of the number of correct predictions and the total number of predictions. These measures were specifically used because of the imbalanced nature of the datasets. Overall accuracy might not be an accurate measurement of performance in these situations. Hence, accuracy of the minority class is considered for evaluating the performance.

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{True Positive} + \text{True Negative}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive} + \text{True Negative} + \text{False Negative}} \quad (4.4)$$

The weighted combination of these two measures would provide an unbiased and clear interpretation of the results. To measure the significance of the results attained by the eSNN model, it is necessary

to compare it with other standard machine learning algorithms. In this study, two popular algorithms are chosen for this purpose.

4.2 Results and Comparison

Before applying our machine learning model on the given data, we need to create a training and test set. We have applied the K-Fold cross-validation to estimate the accuracy of the model. Cross-validation is a resampling procedure used to evaluate machine learning models on a limited data sample. In the proposed computational model, only two parameters (the number of the receptive fields and the parameter β) were optimised. Table 4.1 reports the accuracy and F1-Score obtained with the combination of several parameters on eSNN.

TABLE 4.1: Classification accuracy and F1 score obtained for the case study data with different combinations of parameters.

Parameter Combination	Accuracy %	F1-Score
N=3 & $\beta=1.4$	57.14	0.70
N=4 & $\beta=1.2$	62.46	0.82
N=5 & $\beta=1.1$	71.0	0.73
N=6 & $\beta=1.6$	73.59	0.80
N=7 & $\beta=1.4$	86.46	0.91
N=8 & $\beta=1.6$	70.0	0.77
N=9 & $\beta=1.7$	67.68	0.70

The above results prove that the performance of the eSNN network is largely dependent on parameters. The combination of $\beta = 1.4$, $N = 7$ produced the best classification accuracy for the given test data. With our dataset, the highest classification accuracy for MLP was obtained with 4 hidden layers and 12 neurons at each hidden layer, and the best result for SVM was obtained with polynomial kernels and a degree of 2. These results are reported in Table 4.2.

TABLE 4.2: Comparative analysis of eSNN, SVM and MLP classification algorithms.

Algorithm	Accuracy	F1-Score
eSNN	86.46	0.91
SVM	70.96	0.76
MLP	76.24	0.82

4.3 Signatory Genes

After evaluating the proposed computational model, we decided to extract the signatory genes, which can be used to apply the above computational model. Signatory genes is a group of genes in gene

expression data that is capable of giving similar classification accuracy as of the original data. The signatory genes are a few number genes; sometimes getting the gene data for multiple genes is a time-consuming and challenging task, so with the concept of signatory gene, we can achieve an almost similar result from the computational model using data for only signatory gene. Some of the benefits of getting the signatory genes are that it reduces the computation cost, overcomes the issue of dealing with a large set of features, and makes computation easier.

Based on the signature gene matrix, using genetic algorithm [66], each possible combination of genes were tested in our computational model, and the classification accuracy was observed. A set of five genes achieved an accuracy of around 86.46%. These genes can be used to determine the type of diet for a person and what are their current status and weight. The list of signatures genes is shown in Table 4.3. The gene description is obtained from the online website of GeneCards.

TABLE 4.3: Signatory Genes.

Gene	Description
NDUFB2	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Subunit B2
NDUFS7	NADH:Ubiquinone Oxidoreductase Core Subunit S7
TNNI2	Troponin I2, Fast Skeletal Type
COX8A	Cytochrome C Oxidase Subunit 8A
ATP6V1A	ATPase H ⁺ Transporting V1 Subunit A

4.4 Summary

In this chapter, we have applied the machine learning algorithms on our classification model. We have compared the accuracy of our algorithm with different algorithms and analysed their results. We have observed that the eSNN performs better than SVM and MLP. Based on the accuracy, we also applied the algorithm to select the signature gene using a genetic algorithm, and we got 5 genes as signature gene. These gene give a reasonable accuracy on our computational model, so we can say that we can test the category of diet only with the data of signature genes.

Chapter 5

Conclusion and Future Work

In this research, a computational model is built for analysis of static gene expression data. Additionally, an algorithm is proposed for selection of signature genes. Our results demonstrate that our computational model can help predict weight related issues by assessing gene expression data. For the first time, Gaussian receptive fields are used to encode gene expression data in an eSNN. The method has proven its ability to classify the selected signature genes with a higher classification accuracy, when compared with traditional classification methods. This constitutes a machine based automatic technique for fast and highest classification results, which could find its application in the area of personalised modelling. This research work was also published as a paper [49] in the ICONIP 2018 conference where additional information on the work can be found.

The current work can be applied for classification of diets of people by PBMC sample. It can be also useful for prevention of chronic diseases. We have also been able to find the signature genes for the proposed model[67]. The concept of signature genes can be easily applied to any other similar kind of problem set for feature reduction. It reduces the computation cost as well as it is easy to gather data for only few gene samples.

A natural extension of this project would be to combine the eSNN architecture with a suitable evolutionary algorithm for optimising the remaining parameters of the model (i.e. the modulation factor, spiking and similarity threshold). This would mostly help improve the classification accuracy. With the obtained result we can make a knowledge base which can be useful for deciding the daily diet of a person.

Appendix A

Python Code

The Python code which is used to implement the eSNN architecture is shown below-

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.cross_validation import train_test_split
import math
import sklearn.metrics.pairwise
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler

import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=DeprecationWarning)

from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
from sklearn.metrics import roc_curve
from sklearn.metrics import roc_auc_score
from sklearn.cross_validation import StratifiedKFold

#Import for KNN
from operator import itemgetter
from collections import Counter

#pyCUDA package
import pycuda.autoinit
import pycuda.driver as cuda

#Package for ranking
from scipy.stats import rankdata

#Initializing Learning Parameters
mod_good=0.950
mod_bad=0.950
C_good=0.750
C_bad=0.750
sim_good=0.250
sim_bad=0.0005
```

```

#Initializing Population Encoding Parameters
imin=5
imax=12
gamma=2
no_of_gaussianRP=5
#dimension of data
dimension=raw_data.shape[1]-1
print (dimension)
no_of_pre_neurons=dimension*no_of_gaussianRP
print (no_of_pre_neurons)
dimension_of_repository=no_of_pre_neurons+3
print (dimension_of_repository)
previous_merges_index=no_of_pre_neurons+1
threshold_index=no_of_pre_neurons
class_index=no_of_pre_neurons+2

#Reading PMBC Raw Data
raw_data = pd.read_csv('PMBC_Final.csv',header=0)
raw_data.info()
raw_data.sample(49)

raw_data = raw_data.astype(np.float32)
raw_data.describe()

#splitting the data set
train_data = raw_data[0:34]
test_data = raw_data[35:49]
print(train_data.shape)
print(test_data.shape)

#code to calculate the vlaue of a column
for no. of SFA, MUFA & MED Diet in diet type column
train_data.Label.value_counts()

no_of_cols=len(raw_data.columns)
print (no_of_cols)
print (raw_data.head())

#code to calculate the vlaue of a column for no. of SFA, MUFA & MED Diet in diet type column
test_data.Label.value_counts()

#Actual Test Data
target_data=raw_data.ix[:,no_of_cols-1]
#print target_data.head()
print (raw_data['Label'].unique())

width = []
for col in range(0,dimension):
    width.append((raw_data.iloc[:,col].max()-raw_data.iloc[:,col].min())/
    (gamma*(no_of_gaussianRP-2)))

#width of each column
print (width)

```

```

width_array = np.array(width)
print (width_array)
width_g = width_array.astype(np.float32)
print (width_g)

#values of c
c = []
for col in range(0,dimension):
    c.append((raw_data.iloc[:,col].max()-raw_data.iloc[:,col].min()/(no_of_gaussianRP-2))
c_array = np.array(c)
print(c)
print(c_array)
c_g = c_array.astype(np.float32)
print (c_g)

#min array = minimum values of all columns
minimum = []
for col in range(0,dimension):
    minimum.append(raw_data.iloc[:,col].min())
min_array = np.array(minimum)
print(minimum)
print(min_array)
min_g = min_array.astype(np.float32)
print (min_g)

#####START OF TRAINING FUCNTION#####
# create two timers so we can speed-test each approach
#print(Rank_of_presynaptic_neurons_repository.shape)
start = cuda.Event()
end = cuda.Event()
start.record() # start timing
start.synchronize()
#Initialize Neuron Repository
Neuron_repository_temp_data=np.zeros(shape=[0,dimension_of_repository])
#print Neuron_repository_good_data.shape
#Iterating through rows
for index,row in train_data.iterrows():

    center_list=[]
    firing_time=[]
    simulation_firing_time=[]
    new_weights=[]
    weights=[]
    index_max_similarity=0
    similarity_matrix=[]
    #Iterating through columns
    for col in range(0,dimension):

        center_list=[]
        for i in range(1,(no_of_gaussianRP+1)):
            center_list.append(min_g[col] + (((2*i-3)/2.0) * c_g[col]))

```

```

#finding firing time of neurons
for i in range(0,no_of_gaussianRP):
    center=center_list[i]
    q=math.exp( -(row[col] -center)**2) / (2*(width_g[col]**2)) )
    firing_time.append(math.floor((1 - q)*20))
    #firing_time.append(q)

#print ("Center list = ",center_list)
#print ("firing_time=",firing_time)
#print ("firing_time shape=", np.array(firing_time).shape)
firing_time = np.array(firing_time)
rank_of_presynaptic_neurons = rankdata(firing_time, method= 'dense')
#rank_of_presynaptic_neurons = rank_of_presynaptic_neurons.reshape(1,no_of_pre_neurons)
#Rank_of_presynaptic_neurons_repository = np.concatenate(
(Rank_of_presynaptic_neurons_repository,rank_of_presynaptic_neurons),axis=0)

#Finding weights for the newly created neurons
#print(rank_of_presynaptic_neurons)
new_weights=(mod_good)**rank_of_presynaptic_neurons
#print new_weights.shape

#findig maximum potential
max_potential=np.dot(new_weights,new_weights)
#print max_potential

#Calculate threshold
new_threshold=C_good*max_potential
#print threshold
new_weights=np.insert(new_weights,threshold_index,new_threshold)
new_weights=np.insert(new_weights,previous_merges_index,0)
new_weights=np.insert(new_weights,class_index,row[dimension])
#np.insert(new_weights,22,row['class'])
weights=new_weights.reshape(1,dimension_of_repository)
#print weights.shape
if np.all(Neuron_repository_temp_data==0):
    #print "First Neuron"
    Neuron_repository_temp_data=np.concatenate(
(Neuron_repository_temp_data,weights),axis=0)
else:
    #Finding similarity matrix
    similarity_matrix=sklearn.metrics.pairwise.euclidean_distances(
Neuron_repository_temp_data,weights)
    #print similarity_matrix
    #print similarity_matrix.shape
    #print index_max_sim
    if any(similarity_matrix[0:]<sim_good):
        #print "similarity matrix=",similarity_matrix
        index_max_sim=np.argmin(similarity_matrix)
        #print "Index Similarity=",index_max_sim
        N=Neuron_repository_temp_data[index_max_sim,previous_merges_index]
        old_threshold=Neuron_repository_temp_data[index_max_sim,threshold_index]
        #print "old threshold=",old_threshold
        #print "N=",N
        old_weights=Neuron_repository_temp_data[index_max_sim,0:no_of_pre_neurons-1]

```

```

        #print "Old weights=",old_weights
        Neuron_repository_temp_data[index_max_sim,0:no_of_pre_neurons-1]=(new_weights[0:no_of_p
        (old_weights*N))/(N+1)
        #print "new weights=",Neuron_repository[index_max_sim,0:19]
        Neuron_repository_temp_data[index_max_sim,threshold_index]=(new_threshold+
        (old_threshold*N))/(N+1)
        temp_threshold=Neuron_repository_temp_data[index_max_sim,threshold_index]
        #print "new threshold=",temp_threshold
        Neuron_repository_temp_data[index_max_sim,previous_merges_index]=N+1
        #print "new N=",Neuron_repository[index_max_sim,21]
        #print "======"
    else:
        Neuron_repository_temp_data=np.concatenate(
        (Neuron_repository_temp_data,weights),axis=0)
        #print "No similarity"
        #print "======"

#=====END OF TRAINING FUCNTION=====#
end.record()
end.synchronize()
secs = start.time_till(end)*1e-3
#for i in range(0,num_rows):
    #print(Rank_of_presynaptic_neurons_repository[12])
print ("SNN time:")
print ("%fs" % secs)

nrows_test = len(test_data.index)
#print(nrows)
avg_accuracy_of_tenfold_cv=0.0
avg_accuracy_of_tenfold_cv_KNN=0.0

#Testing Weights
Testing_weights=Neuron_repository_temp_data[0:,0:no_of_pre_neurons]
#Actual test data
actual_test_data=test_data['Label']

#=====Testing Phase=====
Accuracy=0.0
Accuracu_KNN=0.0
actual_class_count=0.0
correct_prediction_count=0.0

predicted_test_data=[]
predicted_test_data_KNN=[]

for index,row in test_data.iterrows():
    #print row[0:4]
    center_list=[]
    firing_time=[]
    simulation_firing_time=[]
    new_weights=[]
    weights=[]

```

```

index_max_similarity=0
similarity_matrix=[]
count_good_class=0
count_bad_class=0
#Iterating through columns
for col in range(0,dimension):
    width=None
    center_list=[]
    width=((raw_data.iloc[:,col].max()-raw_data.iloc[:,col].min()))/
    (gamma*(no_of_gaussianRP-2))
    x=row[col]
    #print "width=",width
    #print("x=",x)
    #finding Center of RP
    for i in range(1,(no_of_gaussianRP+1)):
        b=(2*i-3)/2.0
        #print "b=",b
        c=(raw_data.iloc[:,col].max()-raw_data.iloc[:,col].min())/
        (no_of_gaussianRP-2)
        #print "c=",c
        d=b*c
        #print "d=",d
        center_list.append(raw_data.iloc[:,col].min()+d)
        #print "i=",i
    #finding firing time of neurons
    for i in range(0,no_of_gaussianRP):
        center=center_list[i]
        l=-(x-center)**2
        m=2*(width**2)
        p=l/m
        q=math.exp(p)
        firing_time.append(q)

#print(firing_time)
#finding firing time of neurons using coding interval[delat T]
for i in range(0,no_of_gaussianRP*dimension):
    simulation_firing_time.append(math.floor((1-firing_time[i])*20))

#Ranking of neurons
rank_of_presynaptic_neurons = rankdata(np.array(simulation_firing_time), method= 'dense')
#print(rank_of_presynaptic_neurons)

#Finding weights for the newly created neurons

new_weights=(mod_good)**rank_of_presynaptic_neurons
#print new_weights

#Finding the most similar weight from the Neuron_repository_final
#Finding similarity matrix
similarity_matrix=sklearn.metrics.pairwise.euclidean_distances(
Testing_weights,new_weights)
index_max_sim=np.argmax(similarity_matrix)
#print similarity_matrix.size

```

```

#Findind index of K smaller elements
similarity_matrix_temp=np.reshape(similarity_matrix,

(np.product(similarity_matrix.shape),))
#print similarity_matrix_temp.shape
#====Similarity using KNN Starts here=====
k=11
index_k_max_sim=np.argpartition(similarity_matrix_temp,k)[:k]
#print "index_max_sim=",index_max_sim
#print "index_K_max_sim=",index_k_max_sim
#for ind in index_k_max_sim:
#print Neuron_repository_final[ind,class_index],
#print
for ind in index_k_max_sim:
    if Neuron_repository_temp_data[ind,class_index]==0.0:
        count_good_class=count_good_class+1
    else:
        count_bad_class=count_bad_class+1
if count_good_class>count_bad_class:
    predicted_test_data_KNN.append(0.0)
    #print "Predicted Class=",0.0
else:
    predicted_test_data_KNN.append(1.0)
    #print "Predicted Class=",1.0

#====Similarity using KNN Ends here=====

#Finding the predicted class of test sample
predicted_class=Neuron_repository_temp_data[index_max_sim,class_index]
predicted_test_data.append(predicted_class)

#if row[dimension]==predicted_class:
    #correct_prediction_count=correct_prediction_count+1
    #actual_class_count=actual_class_count+1
    #print "Actual_class=",row[dimension]
    #print "Predicted_class=",predicted_class
    #print "====="
#print "Total Number of Correct Prediction=",correct_prediction_count
#print "Total number of samples=",actual_class_count
#Accuracy=(correct_prediction_count/actual_class_count)
#print "Accuracy=",Accuracy*100
predicted_test_data=np.array(predicted_test_data)
actual_test_data=np.array(actual_test_data)
#print "ACTUAL TEST DATA=",actual_test_data
#print "PREDICTED TEST DATA=",predicted_test_data
#print "Predicted Class Shape=",predicted_test_data.shape
predicted_test_data_KNN=np.array(predicted_test_data_KNN)
Accuracy_Score_KNN=accuracy_score(actual_test_data,predicted_test_data_KNN)
print ("Accuracy Score in percentage(KNN)=",Accuracy_Score_KNN*100)

#print "Confusion Matrix=",confusion_matrix(actual_test_data,predicted_test_data,labels=[0,1])
Accuracy_Score=accuracy_score(actual_test_data,predicted_test_data)

```

```

print ("Accuracy Score in percentage=", Accuracy_Score*100)
print ("===== FOLD OVER =====")

from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix
from sklearn import metrics
print ("No. of GR:", no_of_gaussianRP)
cm1 = confusion_matrix(actual_test_data, predicted_test_data_KNN)
print('Confusion Matrix : \n', cm1)

total1=sum(sum(cm1))
####from confusion matrix calculate accuracy
accuracy1=(cm1[0,0]+cm1[1,1])/total1
print ('Accuracy: ', accuracy1)

specificity1 = cm1[0,0]/(cm1[0,0]+cm1[0,1])
print('specificity: ', specificity1 )

sensitivity1 = cm1[1,1]/(cm1[1,0]+cm1[1,1])
print('Sensitivity: ', sensitivity1)

auc_score = (sensitivity1 + specificity1)/2
print('Auc_score: ', auc_score)

#fpr, tpr, thresholds = metrics.roc_curve(actual_test_data, predicted_test_data_KNN,
pos_label=1)
#print(tpr)
#print (metrics.auc(fpr, tpr))

df = pd.DataFrame(predicted_test_data)
df.to_csv("predicted_test_data.csv")
df1 = pd.DataFrame(actual_test_data)
df1.to_csv("actual_test_data.csv")
print('ddd')

```

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